

EVALUATION OF MICROBIAL CONTAMINANTS IN RETAILED BRANDED BOTTLED AND SACHET WATER IN PUBLIC SUPPLY IN THREE UNIVERSITIES SOUTHWEST NIGERIA

¹Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, ²Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, ³Olubukola Oziegbe, ³Eze Frank Ahuekwe, ¹Abayomi Stephen Akinola, ²Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, ³Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, ⁴Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, ⁵Funmilayo Rufai, ⁶Francis Adewumi Fadiora and ¹Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

¹Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Science, Lagos State University, 102101 Lagos - Nigeria.

Mobile phone: +234-8055055478

²Department of Biological sciences, Faculty of Natural Science, Ajayi Crowther University, 200001 Oyo - Nigeria.

³Department of Biological Science, College of Science and Technology, Covenant University, 112104 Ota - Nigeria.

⁴Department of Biology, University of Nebraska, 5814 Western Ave. 68132 NE, Omaha, USA.

⁵University of New Haven Career Development center, West Haven CT. USA.

⁶Department of Botany, Faculty of Science, Lagos State University, 102101 Lagos - Nigeria.

E-Mail: olusola.ojo-omoniyi@lasu.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15517594>

Keywords:

Bottled water, membrane filtration, microorganisms, public health, sachet water, 16S rDNA

Abstract: Drinking water safety is crucial to public health safety and One-health program being advocated by the world health Organization (WHO) as a means of securing upgrade in the quality of life. A total of twelve retailed branded bottled and sachet water samples were randomly purchased for microbiological analysis from three metropolitan Universities. The physic-chemical properties of these samples were determined prior to microbiological analysis. Standard and conventional methods were followed using the membrane filter technique (diameter 0.45 μ m) for the isolation of microbial contaminants. Microbial isolates were cultured on nutrient agar (NA),

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

*Sabouraud dextrose agar (SDA) and Thiosulphate citrate bile salt sucrose agar (TCBS) simultaneously. Although, biochemical and micro-morphological methods were used for preliminary characterization of these microbial contaminants. The World Health Organization (WHO) and National Food and Drug Administration Council (NAFDAC) standards were the basis of the assessment criteria. Although, the physic-chemical parameters of the analyzed water samples were within the limits stipulated by NAFDAC and WHO, the microbiological quality of the packaged water were compromised. Sachet water samples were found to be more vulnerable to microbial contaminations than bottled water samples. Poor plant sanitation process, Poor handling of products, and poor hygiene among personnel were the reasons for the detection of these contaminants in these products. Molecular characterization of these isolates using the 16S rDNA / ITS method further gave accurate identities of these microbial contaminants. Contrary to previous characterization of some of these contaminants on TCBS medium as *Vibrio cholerae*, they were identified as *Bacillus subtilis* (Ascension number AB 862127.1) and *Bacillus pumilus* (Ascension number EF 491624.1), other isolates included *Micrococcus lylae* (Ascension number MH 393514.1), *Bacillus horneckiae* (Ascension number FR 749913.1). Further scientific surveillance on the water processing plants and packaging method would give incontrovertible evidence of the source of the detected contaminants.*

INTRODUCTION

Water is an important component of every life (Oludairo and Aiyedun, 2016; Edbert *et al.*, 2017) and it is an essential resource for various human activities (Adelodun *et al.*, 2021). Approximately, 1.7 billion children were reported to be affected by diarrhea each year and about 525,000 of these children died each year, besides nearly 1 million adults that are killed by diarrhea every year (Kristanti *et al.*, 2022). In

order to promote healthy living among citizens, a reliable potable water access is essential for sustainable development, healthy food production and poverty alleviation (Balogun *et al.*, 2014; Edbert *et al.*, 2017). However, it has been estimated that over 1.2 billion individuals do not have access to safe and healthy drinking water in the world (Boubetra *et al.*, 2011; Maduka *et al.*, 2014). Most regions of the developing nations are experiencing shortage of

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

potable water supply since improved water sources are only limited to urban areas (Omalu *et al.*, 2010). It is the responsibility of governments to provide safe drinking and food processing water but bottled drinking water has been presumed a healthy alternative to tap water, hence, the rapid increase in water processing factories in recent years (Piyaranthra *et al.*, 2020). Potable water accessibility and supply is limited due to fluctuating climatic conditions and environmental pollution that diminishes the wholesomeness of most water sources (Onyago *et al.*, 2018). Water shortage and pollution of the readily accessible water sources are common issues in many regions of the developing nations (Gangil *et al.*, 2013; Oludairo and Aiyedun, 2016). This is due to inadequate treatment facilities for water and wastes as well as low level of personal hygiene thus giving way to pollution of available water sources (Kuta *et al.*, 2014). Contaminated water sources are vehicles for the transmission of water borne diseases such as cholera, campylobacteriosis, shigellosis and vast majority of diarrheal diseases in the world are attributable to unsafe water, sanitation and personal hygiene issues (Kristanti *et al.*, 2022). Water is susceptible to contamination with microorganisms and organic matter among other pollutants regardless of the source (Gangil *et al.*, 2013; Anyamene and Ojiagu, 2014;

Oludairo and Aiyedun, 2016). There is a rapidly increasing rate of global bottled water consumption, however, urbanization and industrialization have led to the pollution of many water sources worldwide (Qasemi *et al.*, 2018). Bottled water is widely accepted as a reliable healthy drinking water in many parts of the world (Damyanova *et al.*, 2016; Derakhshani *et al.*, 2018; Shams *et al.*, 2019; Piyaranthra *et al.*, 2020). Meanwhile, many sachet water products commonly hawked on streets have also been reported to be contaminated (Oladipo *et al.*, 2009; Akinnibosun and Ugbawa, 2018; Boadi *et al.*, 2023). Microbial contaminants such as *coliforms*, *E. coli*, *Cryptosporidium parvum* and *Giardia / ambliia* compromise the safety of water (Opara and Nnodim, 2014). The detection of *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella* and *Enterobacter* species in branded packaged water suggested poor plant sanitation process as well as poor hygiene on the part of personnel, the detection of pathogens such as *Clostridium perfringens*, *Salmonella* and protozoa in some cases further authenticated the fact that there was faulty quality control mechanism in water treatment plants (Anyamene and Ojiagu, 2014). These pathogens cause diarrhea, giardiasis, dysentery and gastro- enteritis which is common among the rural dwellers of developing nations (Oyedeji *et al.*, 2010; Oludairo and Aiyedun, 2016). World

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

Health Organization (WHO) reported that 80% of all human diseases in developing countries are caused due to infected water consumption (Abera *et al.*, 2011). Most of the diseases in human beings are caused due to unhygienic water supplies used for drink purpose that cause infection like dysentery, diarrhea, cholera, typhoid e.t.c. Currently about 20% world population live with scarcity of safe drinking water and >5 million people die every year from illness associated with drinking water due to inadequate sanitation. Many workers have reported waterborne disease outbreaks due to coliforms and other pathogenic microorganisms (Moore *et al.*, 1993; Mackenzie *et al.*, 1994; Gofti *et al.*, 1999; Adelodun *et al.*, 2021; Boadi *et al.*, 2023). Socioeconomic inequalities in developing countries have been suggested as one of the vital disposing factors to ingestion of poorly treated water for drinking (Adelodun *et al.*, 2021). Although, it has been suggested that point-of-use disinfection of water would enhance the microbiological quality of potable water in public supply as well as public health (Onyango *et al.*, 2018). It can thus be said that safe drinking water is crucial for the well-being of current and future generations.

The objectives of the current study were to determine the microbiological quality of retailed branded bottled and sachet water in circulation

in three metropolitan Universities in southwest Nigeria as well as the identity of the contaminants.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A total of twelve branded retailed bottled water and sachet water samples were obtained from three metropolitan Universities in Lagos and Ogun states, Nigeria. Composite sample of each brand was used in determination of the physico-chemical properties of the samples.

Determination of Physico-chemical properties of water samples

The water samples were subjected aseptically to physico-chemical analysis and microbiological analysis following standard and conventional methods (APHA, 2012).

Microbiological analysis

Membrane filtration technique was used to isolate the microorganisms present in the water samples. The funnel of the membrane filtration unit has a capacity of 50ml and the funnel was mounted on receptacle fixed to the vacuum pump which allowed the water to flow over the porous sterile membrane filter (0.45 μ m) (Hunan BKAMAM Int. Trade Co., Ltd. China). Thereafter, the membrane filters were aseptically placed on each sterile microbial growth medium using sterile forceps after passage of 100ml of water sample through them. The listed microbiological media were prepared and sterilized at 121 $^{\circ}$ C for

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

15 minutes with the autoclave (Unigold Medicals, England); Nutrient agar (HiMedia Laboratories, India), Baired Parker agar (HiMedia Laboratories, India), McConkey agar (Titan Biotech. Ltd. India), plate count agar (HiMedia Laboratories, India), Potato dextrose agar (Biomark Laboratories, India) and Thiosulphate Citrate Bile Salt Sucrose agar (TCBS) (Mast Group Ltd., U.K.) (Gerhardt *et al.*, 1981; APHA, 2005; 2012; Herath *et al.*, 2012).

Morphological and Biochemical characterization of isolates

The morphology of bacterial isolates was studied using $\times 100$ objective lens while fungal isolates were studied using $\times 40$ objective lens of the Electronic Binocular Microscope (Olympus, Japan). Biochemical tests include; Gram staining, Catalase test, Oxidase tests, Coagulase test, Indole test, Endospore staining test and motility test (Gerhardt *et al.*, 1981; Smith, 1981)

DNA extraction

A measurement of 80mg (wet weight) of fungal cell that had been re-suspended in up to 200 μ l of deionized water to a ZR BashingBead™ Lysis Tube was obtained. It was secured in a bead beater fitted with a 2.0ml tube holder assembly (Scientific Industries' Disruptor Genie™, Cat. No. S6001-2 from Zymo Research Corp.) and processed at maximum speed for 5minutes. The ZR BashingBead™ Lysis Tube was centrifuged in a micro-centrifuge (Centrifuge 5424, Eppendorf

AG, Germany) at $\geq 10,000 \times g$ for 1minute. Up to 400 μ l supernatant was transferred to a Zymo-Spin™ IV Spin Filter (orange top) in a Collection Tube and centrifuged at 7,000 rpm (7,000 $\times g$) for 1 minute. The base of the Zymo-Spin™ IV Spin Filter was snapped off prior to use. Approximately, 1,200 μ l of Fungal DNA Binding Buffer was added to the filtrate in the collection tube of step four. Thereafter, 800 μ l of the mixture from step five was transferred to a Zymo-Spin™ IIC Column in a Collection Tube and centrifuged at 10,000 $\times g$ for 1minute. The flow through was discarded from the Collection Tube and step six was repeated. Then, 200 μ l DNA Per-Wash Buffer was added to the Zymo-Spin™ IIC Column in a new Collection Tube and centrifuged at 10,000 $\times g$ for 1minute. Thereafter, 500 μ l Fungal DNA Wash Buffer was added to the Zymo-Spin™ IIC Column and centrifuged at 10,000 $\times g$ for 1minute. The Zymo-Spin™ IIC Column was transferred to a clean 1.5ml micro-centrifuge tube and 100 μ l DNA Elution Buffer was added directly to the column matrix. It was then centrifuged at 10,000 $\times g$ for 30seconds to elute the DNA (Guter and Koshland Jr. 1990).

PCR Amplification of the ITS Gene and Sequencing

Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) was carried out to amplify the ITS gene of the fungal isolates using the primer pair ITS-1 (5'-TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG-3') and ITS-4 (5'-TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC -3'). PCR

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

amplification of the 16S rRNA gene was performed using the following primers:

Forward Primer (with T7 tail):

(5'-
TAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAGTTTGATCC
TGGCTCAG-3')

Reverse Primer: (5'-GYTACCTTGTTACGACTT-
3')

The PCR reaction was carried out using the Solis Biodyne 5× HOT FIREPol Blend Master mix. PCR was performed in 25 µl of a reaction mixture, and the reaction concentration was brought down from 5× concentration to 1× concentration containing 1× Blend Master mix buffer Buffer (Solis Biodyne), 1.5 mM MgCl₂, 200µM of each deoxynucleoside triphosphates (dNTP) (Solis Biodyne), 25pMol of each primer (BIOMERS, Germany) and 2 unit of Hot FIREPol DNA polymerase (Solis Biodyne). Additional Taq DNA polymerase was incorporated into the reaction mixture to make a final concentration of 2.5 units of Taq DNA polymerase, Proofreading Enzyme, 2µl of the extracted DNA, and sterile distilled water was used to make up the reaction mixture. Thermal cycling was conducted in an Eppendorf Vapo protect thermal cycler (Nexus Series Eppendorf, Germany) for an initial denaturation of 95°C for 15 minutes followed by 35 amplification cycles of 30 seconds at 95°C; 1 minute at 58°C and 1 minute 30 Seconds at 72°C. This was followed by a final extension step of 10 minutes at 72°C. The amplification product was separated on a 1.5% agarose gel and electrophoresis was carried out

at 80V for 1 hour 30 minutes. After electrophoresis, DNA bands were visualized by ethidium bromide staining. 100bp DNA ladder was used as DNA molecular weight standard. Thereafter, the 3500XL Genetic Analyzer was engaged (Thermo Scientific, USA) (Guter and Koshland Jr. 1990; Solanki, 2012).

Data Analysis

In order to identify organisms, DNA sequence data generated from this study was blasted against ITS/16S rDNA type strain database on National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI). Threshold for identification was set with reference (Wang *et al.*, 2014), with modification to accommodate species with high congeneric sequence divergence range. An isolate was assigned to species level if the best matching reference species showed ≥98% homology and the next best matching reference species showed at least 0.8% less sequence homology. A strain or isolate was assigned to genus level when there was 95% to 98% homology to the best matching species, or when more than one sequence entry of several species from the same genus showed ≥98% homology. However, sequences with <95% homology to the best match, an assessment of the congeneric sequence divergence range was carried out by blasting an arbitrarily chosen reference sequence of a type organism for the genus of interest against the type organisms' ITS/16S rDNA gene sequence database. The sequence divergence observed in this blast hits was used to adjudge the congeneric sequence divergence range and this range was used to

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

determine the plausibility of the identification for sequences with <95% homology to blast's best match. Where homology fell below 95% and without the support of congeneric sequence divergence value, identification was considered unsuccessful. Phylogeny was constructed to support the identification by ITS sequence using Fast Minimum Evolution algorithm as deployed on NCBI and visualized on MEGA11 (Tamura *et al.*, 2021). The counts of species and genus were utilized as an estimate of species and genus diversity respectively. In the estimation of the species diversity, unidentified isolates were considered as different from the identified species and therefore counted as different species. In the estimation of the genus diversity, as opposed to the treatment in the estimation of species diversity, unidentified isolates were removed from the analysis. Other descriptive and inferential statistics were carried out on R using the following R packages: base (R. Core Team 2021), reshape2 (Wickham 2007), dplyr (Wickham *et al.*, 2021), ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016), ggpubr (Kassambara, 2020), qpcR (Spiess, 2018), knitr (Xie, 2014; Xie, 2015; Xie, 2021). The data wrangling was achieved using Reshape2 and dplyr; inferential statistics were carried out on R base; and data was visualized using ggplot2, ggpubr, qpcR and knitr.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The physic-chemical analysis was done with reagents of analytical grade while the organic carbon determination showed that sample F (1.28%) had the highest concentration while

samples A and C (1.0 %) had the least concentration. The concentration of the salts (SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} and NO_3^-) and NH_4^+ were more in samples E and F. This is suggestive of microbial activities that would result in proliferation of contaminants, this was confirmed by the findings from microbiological analysis of these samples. These samples with high TOC and mineral salts were sachet water samples while those with least concentrations of these chemical ions were Bottled water samples (Table 1). Furthermore, suspended solids (TSS) were found in samples D, E and F which is suggestive of presence of contaminants in these samples (Table 1). The pH value for both Bottled and sachet water samples were the same that is, almost neutral (pH 6.9). This finding was corroborated by the submission of Boadi *et al.* (2024). Most of the water processing factories visited derived both Bottled and Sachet water from the same process line, however, Sachet water often gets contaminated more than Bottled water due to poor hygiene and poor handling by personnel. There were more direct positive correlations of the physico-chemical parameters of samples D, E, F and microbial contaminations, this was also corroborated by Boadi *et al.* (2024). Heavy metals (Pb and Hg) were not found in any of the samples. Inoculation of aliquot samples of each of the water samples on Thiosulphate Citrate Bile Salt Sucrose agar (TCBS) revealed presence of growth when sample D (Sachet water) was analyzed (Table 1). The biochemical tests revealed that only isolate A3 was Gram positive

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

while other bacterial isolates were of the family Enterobacteriaceae (Table 2). The microbial cells in both bottled and sachet water samples were relatively low (Table 3 and 4) but this is not acceptable for Drinking water going by US standards. The percentage occurrence of pathogenic isolates based on the preliminary morphological and biochemical characterization was 25% for each of *Salmonella* sp. and

Escherichia coli (Table 3 and 4). However, molecular characterization of these isolates provided incontrovertible evidence of the identity of these isolates. The presence of fungal isolates was presumably due to poor handling as well as unhygienic practice of personnel involved in the transportation / distribution of the finished product.

Table 1 Physic-chemical analysis of the branded bottled and sachet water

Parameter	A	B	C	D	E	F	Mean & S.D
TOC (%)	1.0	1.2	1.0	1.15	1.25		1.281.15±0.12
NH ₄ ⁺ (Mg/L)	1.45	2.30	3.02	6.30	5.25		8.30
	4.44±2.63						
NO ₃ ⁻ (Mg/L)	0.31	0.40	0.35	1.20	1.46		2.21
	0.99±0.77						
PO ₄ ³⁻ Mg/L	0.02	0.01	0.02	1.22	1.34		1.30
	0.65±0.69						
TSS (Mg/L)	0	0	0	3.20	2.10		5.10
	1.73±2.13						
SO ₄ ²⁻ (Mg/L)	0.03	0.04	0.01	6.34	8.35		5.3
	3.35±3.77						
Pb (Mg/L)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00
	0.00±0.00						
Hg (Mg/L)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00
	0.00±0.00						
pH	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9		6.9
	6.90±0.00						

KEY:

A= Unilag bottled water

B= CU bottled water

C= Lasu bottled water

D= Unilag sachet water

E= CU sachet water

F= Lasu sachet water

TOC =Total organic Carbon

TSS=Total suspended solid

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

Analysis of Variance Table for the Data

Source	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	13	23.831	11.464	0.000
Intercept	1	245.803	118.244	0.000
Parameter	8	32.428	15.599	0.000
Location	5	10.077	4.848	0.001
Error	40	2.079		
Total	54			
Corrected Total	53			

a. R Squared = .788 (Adjusted R Squared = .720)

Homogeneous Subsets Values Using Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT)

Parameter	N	Subset			
		1	2	3	4
Duncan ^{a,b}					
Pb	6	0.0000			
Hg	6	0.0000			
PO	6	0.6517			
NO	6	0.9883			
TOC	6	1.1467			
TSS	6	1.7333	1.7333		
SO	6		3.3450	3.3450	
NH	6			4.4367	
pH	6				6.9000
Sig.		0.073	0.060	0.197	1.000

**a is more significant than b*

SD (Standard deviation)

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

Isolate code	Gram reaction	shape	catalase	coagulase	oxidase	Indole	Methyl/red	Voges-Proskauer	Urease	H ₂ S	Glucose	Fruose	Lactose	Sucrose	Galactose	Probable identity
A1	—	R	+	ND	-	+	-	+	-	+	AG	ND	A	A	AG	<i>Salmonella sp.</i>
A2	—	R	+	ND	-	+	+	-	-	ND	A	A	A	A	ND	<i>E. coli</i>
A3	+	C	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	ND	A	A	-	A	ND	<i>S. aureus</i>
A4	-	R	+	ND	-	-	-	+	-	+	AG	A	A	A	ND	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
A5	-	Cm	+	ND	+	+	ND	+	-	-	A	AG	A	A	ND	<i>V. cholerae</i>
A6	-	R	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	AG	AG	A	A	AG	<i>Klebsiella sp.</i>
A7	-	R	+	ND	-	-	+	+	-	-	AG	A	-	A	A	<i>Flavobacterium sp.</i>

Table 2 Morphological and Biochemical Characterization of the isolated microorganisms

Key:

R= rods

C=cocci

Cm=comma

ND=Not Determined

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

Table 3: Percentage Occurrence of Isolated Microorganisms

Isolated organisms	Number of occurrences	Percentage of occurrence (%)
<i>Salmonella spp.</i>	3	25
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	3	25
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	2	16.7
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	1	8.3
<i>V. cholera</i>	1	8.3
<i>Klebsiella spp.</i>	1	8.3
<i>Flavobacterium spp.</i>	1	8.3
TOTAL	20	

Table 3 Analysis (T-Test)

	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Interval Difference Lower	Confidence of the Upper
Number of Occurrence	4.768	6	0.003	1.71429	0.8346	2.5940

TABLE 4 Distribution of Microorganisms Isolated from Water Samples

Isolated organism	Lasu (S1)	Unilag (S2)	Covenant (S3)
<i>Salmonella sp.</i>	+	+	+
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	+	+	+
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	+	+	-
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	-	-	+
<i>V. cholera</i>	-	+	-
<i>Klebsiella sp.</i>	-	-	+
<i>Flavobacterium sp.</i>	-	+	-
TOTAL	3	5	4

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

Fig. 1: Phylogeny tree of *Bacillus subtilis*

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

Fig. 2: Phylogeny tree of *Bacillus pumilus*

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

Fig. 3: Phylogeny tree of *Micrococcus lylae*

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

Fig. 4: Phylogeny tree of *Bacillus horneckiae*

Morphological and biochemical examination of the isolated contaminants confirmed presence of coliforms, *Flavobacterium* sp. and *Staphylococcus aureus* (Table 2) whose presence was traceable to the imperfect handling and poor hygiene of personnel since all the Bottled samples did not have this challenge. The biochemical

characterization of one of the contaminants as *Vibrio cholerae* resulted in the need for molecular characterization of these contaminants. Contrary evidence was provided through molecular characterization of the same isolate as *Bacillus subtilis*. Although, the detected contaminants were relatively few in number having the WHO and US standards as reference but they were of

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

significant public health importance (Table 3). The distribution process of packaged water samples often exposes these products to many hazards associated with contamination of the product particularly in developing countries. These products were randomly procured from restaurants in metropolitan Universities, southwest Nigeria and that suggested that large population of students drank these packaged water samples, nearby communities and University community source the drinking water for their families from these wholesale points (Table 4).

Provision of safe drinking water is critical and this must be made available to citizens for public health safety. The presence of coliforms in all the branded bottled and sachet water product, although, at low concentration suggested the poor quality of drinking water in public supply which corroborated the reports of Akinnibosun and Ugbawa (2017); Oladipo *et al.*, (2009). The relatively high TOC percentage in the sachet water products makes them vulnerable to coliforms invasion and other pathogenic microorganisms. Although, the branded bottled water is expected to be void of microbial contaminants however, the detection in sample D of a single cell of *V. cholerae* through biochemical characterization makes the sample a health risk. This finding further corroborated the conclusion of Pluym *et*

al. (2024). The number of pathogenic bacteria isolated from the composite sample of each branded bottled water was relatively small, however, it made them unsuitable for public consumption (WHO, 2001). The H⁺ ion index of both types of packaged water products in public circulation were within the limits set by National Food and Drug Administration Council (NAFDAC) and WHO (WHO, 2001). The detection of *E. coli* and *Klebsiella sp.* in some of the branded water products based on biochemical characterization suggested that some of the samples may have been contaminated from fecal sources and as such were not safe for public consumption (WHO, 2001; Oludairo and Aiyedun, 2016). Comparatively, the biochemical characterization results were not as strong as molecular characterization which were incontrovertible. The biochemical method of characterization may sometimes not be the final evidence for identification of microbial contaminants where microbiological quality of potable is in question.

Although, biofilm formation, loose deposit accumulation and water quality deterioration in drinking water may be from distribution lines into the factory. Hence, the presence of suspended solids in drinking water can subsequently breed pathogenic bacteria in bottled and sachet water products (Liu *et al.*, 2017). The detection of

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

organic Carbon in processed packaged water products may compromise the quality of the water and subsequently influence the growth of pathogenic bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* (Shams *et al.*, 2019; Edbert, *et al.*, 2017). Although, many packaged water products were produced in agreement with specified industry standards, the process of its distribution often compromise the microbiological quality of the branded products and subsequently jeopardize the public health safety (Pluym *et al.*, 2024). Hence, the need for the suggested point – of - use water disinfection strategy by Onyago *et al.* (2018). The biochemical characterization of the fungal isolates detected in the course of evaluation of retailed packaged water products showed that poor hygiene of personnel and the distribution network adopted may subsequently influence the quality of drinking water in circulation (Pluym *et al.*, 2024). Gene sequencing of selected microbial contaminants would give the accurate genetic data of the microorganisms involved. Sustainable potable water monitoring and distribution for public consumption would be achieved when appropriate actions are taken by both regulatory agencies and WHO as well as standard practice by water processing plant to bring the import of health education to every home as well as the integration of the sustainable

development goals (SDG) into every day learning in the crèche, colleges and tertiary institutions.

CONCLUSION

The water quality failure with the selected premium branded bottled and sachet water products from three metropolitan Universities in Nigeria reflected what obtained in the larger society. All bottled and sachet water products that failed compliance with NAFDAC and WHO regulations should be retreated before they are released to the public for consumption. Therefore, surveillance of packaged water manufacturing factories by regulatory agencies is mandatory to ensure strict compliance with Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP) as well as WHO standards in addition to effective health education for both personnel and the public.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to Dr. Oluwole Odetunmibi, Department of Mathematics, College of Science & Technology (CST), Covenant University, Ota – Nigeria. He assisted with all the statistical analysis. We are also grateful to Dr. Ola-Gbadamosi and Mr. Olusola Tijani, Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Science, Lagos State University, Lagos – Nigeria for their assistance.

STATEMENTS AND DECLARATIONS

Funding: The authors declare that no funds, grants, or other support were received during the

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

preparation of this manuscript. This is self-funded research by the listed Authors.

Competing Interests: The authors have no competing interest to disclose because this study was self-sponsored by all the listed authors as a collaborative study. The authors did not receive support from any organization for the conduct of the study and the submitted manuscript.

Author Contributions: The study was conceptualized, designed and preparations by Ojo-Omoniyi, O. A., Olanbiwoninu, A. A. and Fashogbon, R. while data collections, analysis and editing were made by Ahuekwe, E. F., Oziegbe, O., Akinola, S. A., Oniha, I.M., Jamiu, Q. O., Rufai, F. and Fadiora, F. A. All authors contributed equally in the editing of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Dataset: All Dataset are available in GenBank and NCBI repository, the Accession numbers for isolates are displayed and trackable. (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genome).

Ethical Consent: Ethical approval is not required for this type of work in Nigeria, since we did not test any material on human and animal subjects.

Consent to Participate: The consent to participate in this study was given by each author.

Consent to Publish: The consent of each author was obtained prior to the commencement of the publishing process.

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

REFERENCES

- Abera, S., Zeyinuidin, A., Kebede, B., Deribew, A., Ali, S., & Zemene, E., (2011). Bacteriological analysis of drinking water source. *Afr. J. Microbiol. Res.* 5(18): 2638-2641.
- Adelodun, B., Ajibade, F. O., Ighalo, J. O., Odey, G., Ibrahim, R. G., Kareem, K. Y., Bakare, H. O., Tihamiyu, A. O., Ajibade, T. F., Abdulkadir, T.S., Adeniran, K. A. & Choi, K. S. (2021). Assessment of socioeconomic inequality based on virus-contaminated water usage in developing countries: A review. *Environmental Research* 192(110309).
- Akinnibosun, F. I. & Ugbawa, L. A. (2018). Comparative analysis of bottled water and sachet water sold in urban and rural areas of Edo state, Nigeria. *Sierra Leone Journal of Biomedical Research* 9(2): 19 – 27.
- Anyamene, N. C. & Ojiagu, D. K. (2014). “Bacteriological Analysis of sachet water sold in Akwa Metropolis, Nigeria,” *International Journal of Agriculture and Biosciences*, 3: 120–122.
- APHA (2012). *AWWA and Water Environment Federation, Standard Methods for the*

Examination of Water and Wastewater, American Public Health Association, Washington DC, USA, 14 editions.

Balogun, S. A., Akingbade, A. O., Oyekunle, M. A. & Okerentugba, P. O. (2014). “Physiochemical and Microbiological profile of drinking water sold in Abeokuta, Ogun State,” *Nigeria Nature and Science*, 12: 103–105.

Boadi, N. O., Saah, S.A., Badu, M., Baa-Poku, F., Odame, F. & Sakyi, P. O. (2023). Assessment of Sachet water quality in Kumasi, Ghana. *Discover Water* 3:24. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43832-023-0048-8>

Boubetra, A., Nestour, F. L., Allaert, C. & Feinberg, M. (2011). “Validation of alternative methods for the analysis of drinking Water and their application to *Escherichia coli*,” *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 77(10): 3360–3367.

Damyanova, S., Ivanova, I. & Yocheva, L. (2016). Microbiological safety of bottled natural mineral water. *J. Environ. Prot. Ecol.* 17: 896-902.

Derakhshani, E., Naghizadeh, A., Yari, A. R., Mohammadi, M. J., Kamranifar, M. & Farhang, M. (2018). Association of toxico-chemical and microbiological quality of bottled mineral water in Birjand city, Iran. *Toxin Rev.* 37: 138–143.

Edbert, D.C., A. U. Sandra, A. U., & Ebere, E. C. (2017). “Storage and its Effect on Chemical Quality Indicators in Sachet Water Brands Sold in Owerri Municipal,” *Journal of World News of Natural Sciences*, 12: 73–81.

Gangil, R., Tripathi, R., Patyal, A., Dutta, P. & Mathur, K. N. (2013). “Bacteriological evaluation of packaged bottled water sold at Jaipur city and its public health significance,” *Veterinary World.* 6(1): 27–30.

Gerhardt, P., Murray, R. G. E., Costilow, R. N., Nester, E.W., Wood, W. A., Krieg, N. R. & Phillips, G. B. (1981). *Manual of methods for General Bacteriology*. American Society for Microbiology Pp. 524.

Gofti, L., Zmirou, D., Murandi, F.S., Hartemann, P. & Poletton, J. L. (1999). Waterborne microbiological risk assessment: a state of

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

the art and perspectives. *Rev. Epidominol. Sante Public.*, 47: 61-75.

Guter, R. L. & Koshland Jr. D. E. (1990). The molecule of the year. *Science*, 246:1543-1544.

Herath, A.T., Abayasekara, C. L., Chandrajith, R. & Adikaram, N. K. B. (2012). Temporal variation of Microbiological and chemical quality of Noncarbonated Bottled Drinking water sold in Sri Lanka. *Journal of Food Science* 77(3): M160 – M164. DOI:10.1111/j.1750 – 3841.2011.02588.x

Kassambara, A. (2020). ggpubr: 'ggplot2' Based Publication Ready Plots. R package version 0.4.0. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=ggpubr>.

Kuta, G., Emigilati, M., Hassan, A. & Ibrahim, I. (2014). “Domestic water sources and its health implication in Lapai Local Government area, Niger State, Nigeria,” *Ethiopian Journal of Environmental Studies and Management*, 7(6): 686.

Liu, G., Tao, Y., Zhang, Y., Lut., M., Knibbe, W., Wielen, P. Liu, W., Medema, G. & Meer, W. (2017). Hotspots for selected metal elements and microbes' accumulation and

the corresponding water quality deterioration potential in unchlorinated drinking water distribution system. *Water Research* 124: 435 – 445.

Mackenzie, W.R., Hoxie, N.J., Proctor, M.E., Gradus, M.S., Blair, K.A., Peterson, D.E., Kazmierczak, J. J., Addiss, D. G. & Fox, K. R. (1994). A massive outbreak in Milwaukee of *Cryptosporidium* infection transmitted through the public water supply. *N. Engl. J. Med.*, 331: 161-167.

Maduka, H., Chukwu, N., C. Ugwu, C. *et al.*, (2014) “Assessment of Commercial Bottled Table and Sachet Water Commonly Consumed In: Federal University Of Technology, Owerri (FUTO), Imo State, Nigeria Using Microbiological Indices.,” *IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences*, 13(1): 86–89.

Moore, A. C., Herwaldt, B. L., Craun, G. F., Calderon, R. L., Highsmith, A.K. & Juranek, D. D. (1993). Surveillance for waterborne disease outbreaks-United States, 1991-1992. *MMWR CDC Surveillance Summary*. 19. 42(5):1-22.

Oludairo, O. & Aiyedun, J. (2016). “Contamination of commercially packaged

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

- sachet water and the public health implications: an Overview,” *Bangladesh Journal of veterinary medicine*, 13(2):73–81.
- Omalu, I. C. J., Eze, G. C., Olayemi, I. K., Gbesi, S., Adeniran, L. A., Ayanwale, A. V., Mohammed, A. Z., & Chukwuemeka, V. (2010). Contamination of Sachet Water in Nigeria: Assessment and Health Impact. *Online J. Health and Allied Sci.* 9(4):15
- Oladipo, I. C., Onyenike, I. C., & Adebisi, A. O. (2009). Microbiological analysis of some vended sachet water in Ogbomoso, Nigeria. *African journal of Food science* 3:406-12.
- Onyango, A. E., Okoth, M. W., Kunyanga, C. N. & Aliwa, B. O. (2018). Microbiological quality and Contamination level of water sources in Isiolo County in Kenya. *Journal of Environmental and Public Health*. Volume 2018 Article ID 2139867 10p.
- Opara, A. U., & Nnodim, J. (2014). “Prevalence of Bacteria in bottled and sachet water sold in Owerri metropolis,” *International Journal of Science Innovations and Discoveries*, (4): 117– 122.
- Oyededeji, O., Olutiola, P. O. & Moninuola, M. A. (2010). “Microbiological quality of packaged drinking water brands marketed in Ibadan metropolis and Ile-Ife city in South Western Nigeria,” *African Journal of Microbiology Research*, 4(1): 096–102.
- Piyarathna, H. M. R. W., Perera, M. S. C., Karunanyaka, M. P., Elkanayaka, S. S. & Udara, S. P. R. (2020). Sri Lankan Bottled water Industry overview. *Journal of Research Technology and Engineering* 1(1):54–62.
- Pluym, T., Waegenaar, F., Gussemé, B. D. & Boon, N. (2024). Microbial drinking water monitoring now and, in the future. *Microbial biotechnology* 17: e14532. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1751-7915.14532>
- Qasemi, M., Afsharnia, M., Zarei, A. Farhang, M. & Allahdadi, M. (2018). Non-carcinogenic risk assessment to human health due to intake of fluoride in the groundwater in rural areas of Gonabad and Bajestan, Iran: a case study, *Hum. Ecol. Risk Assess.* 1–12.
- R Core Team (2021). R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing,

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

- Vienna, Austria. URL <https://www.R-project.org/>.
- Shams, M., Qasemi, M., Afsharina, M., Mohammadzadeh, A. & Zarei, A. (2019). Chemical and microbial quality of bottled drinking water in Gonabad city, Iran: Effect of time and storage conditions on microbial quality of bottled water. *MethodsX* 6:273-277.
- Smith, G. (1981). *Smith's Introduction to Industrial Mycology 7th edition* (Eds.) A. H. S. Onions, D. Allsopp & H. O. W. Eggins. Publ. Pitman Press, Bath. Sjöstrom Pp.125-152.
- Solanki, G. (2012). Polymerase Chain Reaction. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research* 2(3):98-102.
- Spiess, A. (2018). qpcR: Modelling and Analysis of Real-Time PCR Data. R package version 1.4-1. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=qpcR>
- Tamura, K., Stecher, G., & Kumar, S. (2021) MEGA11: Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis version 11. *Molecular Biology and Evolution* 38:3022-3027.
- Wang, X., Fu, Y. F., Wang, R. Y., Li, L., Cao, Y. H., Chen, Y. Q., ... & Zhu, L. P. (2014). Identification of clinically relevant fungi and prototheca species by rRNA gene sequencing and multilocus PCR coupled with electrospray ionization mass spectrometry. *PLoS One*, 9(5): e98110. World Health Organisation (WHO) (2001). *Water Quality Guidelines, Standard and Health*. IWA Pub. London U.K. ISBN1900222280.
- World Health Organization. (2005). *The WHO report 2005- makes every mother and child count* Geneva: The organization 2005.
- Wickham, H. (2007). Reshaping Data with the reshape Package. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 21(12):1-20. URL <http://www.jstatsoft.org/v21/i12/>.
- Wickham, H. (2016) *ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis*. Springer-Verlag New York.
- Wickham, H., François R., Henry, L., & Müller, K., (2021). *dplyr: A Grammar of Data Manipulation*. R package version 1.0.7. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=dplyr>

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi

Advance Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology

Adv. J. Sci. Eng. Tech

Volume:10; Issue: 3

March-2025

ISSN: 2330 – 1744

Impact Factor: 7.97

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajset/index.php/ajset>

Xie, Y. (2014). knitr: A Comprehensive Tool for Reproducible Research in R. In: *Victoria Stodden, Friedrich Leisch and Roger D. Peng, (editors) Implementing Reproducible Computational Research*. Chapman and Hall/CRC. ISBN 978-1466561595.

Xie, Y. (2015). *Dynamic Documents with R and knitr*. (2nd edition). Chapman and Hall/CRC. ISBN 978-1498716963

Xie, Y. (2021). knitr: A General-Purpose Package for Dynamic Report Generation in R. R package version 1.36.

Olusola Abayomi Ojo-Omoniyi, Afolake Atinuke Olanbiwoninu, Olubukola Oziegbe, Eze Frank Ahuekwe, Abayomi Stephen Akinola, Racheal Oluwayemisi Fashogbon, Margaret Ikhiwili Oniha, Qudus Olatunji Jamiu, Funmilayo Rufai, Francis Adewumi Fadiora and Dr. Olusola Ojo-Omoniyi